

ISic3666

I.Sicily inscription 3666

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

tuff

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Sanctuary of the Malophoros (excavated 1919)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ONIS

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 120885

Bibliography

Gabrics, E. 1927. Il Santuario della Malophoros a Selinunte. *Monumenti Antichi*. 32: 5-419. At 384 no.10

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 219

Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 135 no.15

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